

FABRICATION AND PROPERTY STUDY OF POLYMER/FIBER/CLAY TERNARY COMPOSITES

X. Li*, H.W. Gu, S.Y. Wong, S.L. Chen, X.K. Zhang, Y.Y. Chieng

Synthesis and Integration Capability Group, Institute of Materials Research and Engineering,
Agency for Science, Technology and Research (A*STAR), 3 Research Link, Singapore 117602

* Corresponding author (x-li@imre.a-star.edu.sg)

Keywords: *Ternary Composite; Mechanical Property; Impact Resistance; Nanoclay*

1 General Introduction

Polymer composites reinforced by short fiber, such as glass fiber and carbon fiber, are widely used in automotive industry in place of a number of metallic components owing to lightweight, process-ability, low-cost and ability to tailor their properties for different applications. In general, high fiber loadings are employed to impart great strength and stiffness to the composites. This, however, results in reduced impact resistance of these materials, thus limit their use to only non- or low-impact applications.

Elastomers/soft polymers have been used as additives to improve the impact resistance of short fiber reinforced polymer composites. The soft elastomeric phases present in the composite matrix act as impact absorbers to substantially increase the impact resistance of the material. However, gain in impact resistance normally compromises other properties such as strength, stiffness, chemical resistance or thermal characteristics [1]. Being soft, the incorporated elastomers/soft polymers may lead to significant reduction in composite strength and stiffness. Therefore, it is desirable to develop a novel approach to improve the impact resistance of short fiber reinforced polymer composites without comprise other property.

Natural sourced clay has gained much attention to reinforce polymers in both academic and industrial areas, due to their enhanced properties such as physical, mechanical, barrier and anti-flammable properties [2]. Recently, we have developed a “slurry-compounding” approach for epoxy/clay composite preparation [3,4]. The most significant feature of the new technique is that at little amount (<3 wt%) of modified clay, obvious enhancement on both the modulus and toughness of epoxy are achieved simultaneously.

In this study, clay prepared by modified “slurry-compounding” approach is employed to fabricate

polymer/fiber/clay ternary composite with excellent comprehensive mechanical property, especially impact resistance.

2 Experiments

2.1 Clay modification

5.5 g of dry clay powder is dispersed and swelled in 150 ml of deionised (DI) water for a few hours under stirring. 0.2 ml of acetic acid is then added to the suspension, after which the suspension is stirred for another 30 mins, sonicated for 30 mins in an ultrasonic water-bath and stirred again for 12 hrs. The aqueous clay suspension is then homogenized by a high-speed shear homogenizer for 15 mins, poured into 700 ml of acetone under homogenization, and further homogenized again for 5 mins. Next, the resulting acetone/water clay suspension is filtered and the gelatinous clay residue is redispersed in 700 ml of acetone. The acetone-clay suspension is then homogenized again for 5 mins and filtered. The final gelatinous clay residue obtained is redispersed in 400 ml of acetone to which 0.26 ml of (3-glycidyloxypropyl)trimethoxy silane is added. This suspension is then stirred for 12 hrs at room temperature, sonicated for 30 mins in an ultrasonic water-bath and stirred again for 24 hrs at 53 °C. Following that, excess acetone is removed from the acetone-clay suspension by stirring the suspension at 73 °C until 200 g of clay suspension is obtained. 90 g of DI water is then added to the suspension, which is left to stir again for 2 hr. After that, a solution containing 3.96 g of epoxy in 10 g of acetone is added to the aqueous/acetone clay suspension. The suspension is then homogenized for 1 hr. Next, acetone and water are removed from the homogenized suspension by rotary evaporation until 100 ml of

aqueous clay suspension remains. This suspension is frozen at -20 °C for 24 hrs, and then at -80 °C for another 24 hrs. The frozen clay suspension is freeze-dried for 3 days. The solid residue obtained is then further dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C for a few days.

2.2 Melt-compounding of modified clay with Polyamide 6 and glass fibre

Polyamide/glass-fiber/clay ternary composite with the desired filler loading is fabricated by melt-compounding a fixed amount of dried exfoliated surface-modified clay powder with polyamide/glass-fiber composite pellets in a twin-screw extruder. The resulting polyamide/glass-fiber/clay ternary composite material is then chopped into pellets for subsequent processing and use. As an example, polyamide/glass-fiber composite and polyamide/glass-fiber/clay ternary composites containing 2, 3, 4 and 5 % of clay by weight, hereby named PGCE, PGCE2, PGCE3, PGCE4 and PGCE5 respectively, were prepared via melt-compounding in a twin-screw extruder (L/D = 25; D = 16mm) (Eurolab 16 Twin Screw Extruder, Thermo Scientific) at a screw speed of 200 rpm. The screws consisted of 2 mixing zones with 12 compounding elements in each zone. The temperatures employed along the barrel during extrusion from the inlet to the die were 250, 250, 250, 255, 255 and 255 °C. The extruded composites were air-cooled and pelletized. Composite films were prepared from the extruded pellets of each sample by hot-pressing them at 220 °C for 10 mins under a pressure of 60 bars using a laboratory press (P 200E, Dr Collin GmbH). The following characterization studies were done on the above samples and the results obtained are discussed in the following section.

2.3 Mechanical testing and characterization

Tensile testing of composites obtained was conducted on the standard tensile test bars at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min using a 10 kN load cell in a Instron Universal Tester 5569. 3-Point bending (flexural) testing of composites obtained was conducted on the standard rectangular test bars at a crosshead speed of 13.65 mm/min using a 10 kN load cell in a Instron Universal Tester 5569. Izod impact testing was conducted on the

standard single-edge notch impact test bars in a Zwick Roell Pendulum impact testor HIT25P.

Composite pellets were dried overnight at 80 °C in a vacuum oven and injection molded into tensile, flexural and impact test bars using an injection molding machine (Haake Mini Jet II, Thermo Scientific). Temperature of the cylinder was set at 280 °C and the composite melts were injected at 600 bars in 20 s into a 120 °C mold and a post injection pressure of 300 bars was maintained for 10 s.

TEM observation of thin sections of the composites was performed with a JEOL 2100 TEM under an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. Thin sections with thickness of about 50 nm of the composite film were cut from the prepared composite test bars under cryogenic conditions using a Leica ultramicrotome equipped with a diamond knife. SEM image of the cross-section of composite test bars was examined using a field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL JSM-6700F).

Composite sheets were prepared from the extruded pellets of each polyamide reinforced with modified clay and glass fibre binary filler by hot-pressing at 220 °C for 10 mins under a pressure of 60 bars using a laboratory press (P 200E, Dr Collin GmbH). Hot-pressed composite sheets were mounted onto a sample holder with double-sided sticky tape prior to XRD analysis. Diffraction angle (2θ) of each sample was measured from 2.5 to 30 ° using a X-ray diffractometer (D8 GADDS XRD, Bruker) at 40 kV and 40 mA with Cu-K α radiation as the X-ray source and data acquisition time of 10mins per sample.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Fabrication of polyamide/glass-fiber/clay ternary composites

The polyamide/glass-fibre/clay ternary composite with excellent comprehensive mechanical properties is prepared with novel clay nanofiller that is fabricated from pristine montmorillonite (MMT) through surface modification and intercalation. During preparing, MMT clay sheets are chemically modified with silane and interstitial gaps between clay sheets are filled up with epoxy resin, resulting in producing a surface-modified intercalated clay

nanopowder according to our previous study [3]. Subsequent melt-compounding the obtained nanopowder with polyamide/glass-fibre composite pellets in a twin-screw extruder can produce polyamide/glass-fibre/clay ternary composite. The interfacial interaction of polyamide/glass-fibre and polyamide/clay are both improved by epoxy resin, at the other side, the clay sheets are further intercalated by polyamide

Pristine MMT clay is hydrophilic and can be dispersed into water to form a stable suspension under homogenization, in which clay is dispersed as isolated sheets or small domains consisting of a few sheets. A slightly acidic adjustment of the suspension by adding drops of acetic acid can help to disperse and stabilize the clay sheets. This stable dispersion state of clay in water can be transferred to clay/acetone slurry through exchanging water with acetone, and the exchanging process includes pouring the water suspension into acetone followed by homogenizing for a while, filtering off the mixed water/acetone solvent followed by washing with acetone, and re-dispersing the obtained slurry into acetone under homogenization for a while. To improve the interfacial interaction between clay sheets and polyamide, glycidoxy functional group is introduced onto the surface of clay sheets by adding (3-glycidoxypropyl)trimethoxysilane into the obtained clay/acetone slurry and stirring at room temperature for 3 to 24 hours. Excess amount of acetone is removed by mild heating the slurry under stirring and water is added again under homogenization in order to disperse and swell the silane-modified clay sheets. Subsequently, epoxy resin in acetone is further added in the clay/acetone/water slurry under stirring and homogenizing, followed by rotary evaporation to remove most acetone and generate clay/epoxy/water slurry. The epoxy resin molecules can gradually penetrate into the inter-layer gaps of clay sheets and be retained inside during the evaporating of acetone. As water existing in the clay slurry, the clay sheets intercalated by epoxy resin remain swelled morphology and the clay suspension is frozen and freeze-dried for 3 days. The solid residue obtained is then further dried in a vacuum oven at 60°C. Such surface-modified clay could also be achieved through spray-drying.

Polyamide/glass-fibre composite pellets are completely dried in vacuum oven at 80°C overnight before compounding with modified clay powder. Polyamide/glass-fiber/clay ternary composite with the desired filler loading is fabricated by melt-compounding a fixed weight ratio of dried modified clay powder to dried polyamide/glass-fiber composite pellets in a twin-screw extruder. The content of clay in ternary composite can be controlled by adjusting the feeding rate ratio of polyamide/glass-fiber pellets and clay that are fed at different feeding ports. Alternatively, clay of desired amount can be pre-mixed with polyamide/glass-fiber pellets and fed together. Both methods are equally effective and applicable based on our experiments. As reported, twin-screw extruder with stronger mixing effect is more suitable to obtain nanocomposite with excellent mechanical properties due to better disperse of nanofillers in polymer matrix. However, glass-fibre will be shortened further as using such melt-compounding situation, leading to significant decrease of mechanical performance. Therefore, a good balance between disperse of nanoclay and retain of length of glass-fibre is critical. In this invention, a Eurolab 16 Twin Screw Extruder (Thermo Scientific) with $L/D = 25$ and $D = 16$ mm, screws consisting 3 mixing zones is used to produce all composites as mentioned above. At high temperatures during melt-compounding, the glycidyl group on silane and epoxy molecules will react with the $-NH_2$ or $-COOH$ groups on polyamide to form chemical bonds. The resulting ternary composite contains well-dispersed clay platelets that are uniformly and randomly distributed among, and chemically bound to, the polymer matrix as well as the glass fibers. Glass fibers and clay platelets impart high strength and modulus to the ternary composite while uniform distribution, large interfacial area, strong interfacial interaction and chemical adhesion between clay platelets and composite matrix as well as chemical bonding among clay platelets confer high impact resistance by impeding the propagation of cracks through the material. This ternary composite material can then be processed into articles using conventional thermoplastic processing and manufacturing technology.

3.2 Mechanical property evaluation of ternary composites

Fig 1. Tensile properties of Polyamide 6/glass-fiber/clay ternary composite at different clay content.

To evaluate the mechanical properties of ternary composites, standard tensile test, 3-point bending test and single-edge Izod impact test are conducted following ASTM procedures. Significant increase of Young's modulus, tensile strength, tensile ductility (elongation at break) and strain energy absorbed at failure can be observed. The increment of above properties can reach as high as 31, 24, 26 and 39% at clay content of 3 wt%, respectively. In terms of

flexural modulus, a maximum increase of 12.4% can also be found. Unlike most reported work, the addition of modified clay in the polyamide/glass-fibre composite doesn't result in a typical drop in impact resistance of composite. In contrast, the ternary composites show a unique increase of impact strength up to 30% at clay of 2 wt% compared to neat polyamide/glass-fibre composite without clay.

Fig. 2. Flexural properties of Polyamide 6/glass-fiber/clay ternary composite at different clay content

3.3 Morphology study of ternary composites

Fig. 3. SEM images of cross-section of test bars of glass fibre-reinforced polyamide 6 (a and b) and polyamide 6/glass-fiber/clay composites (c and d, clay: 3 wt%, glass fibre: 15 wt%). Highlighted area by blue circle (in Fig. 3d) demonstrates residual partial bonding between polyamide 6 and glass fibre after tension failure.

SEM images of the cross section of broken tensile specimen bar of composites demonstrate the different polyamide/glass-fiber interfacial interaction as shown in Fig. 3. While a smooth glass fiber surface is observed with polyamide/glass-fiber composites, a thick polyamide layer is wrapped at the surface of glass fibre in polyamide/glass-fiber/clay composites, indicating significant increase of interfacial interaction between polyamide and glass fibre in the presence of modified clay. The uniform clay distribution as well as intercalated structure of clay sheets in polyamide/glass-fiber/clay composites is confirmed by observing cross sectioned composites using TEM as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig.4. TEM images of polyamide 6/glass-fiber/clay composites. (clay: 3 wt%, glass fibre: 15 wt%) at low magnification (Fig. 2a) and high magnification (Fig. 2b).

4 Conclusions

Simultaneous reinforcing and toughening effect can be realized by melt compounding a few percent of specifically modified clay into polyamide/glass-fibre composite. Glass fibers and clay platelets impart high strength and modulus to the ternary composite due to their strong interfacial bonding to polyamide matrix as shown in SEM study. Uniform distribution of clay and strong interfacial interaction between clay platelets and composite matrix as well as chemical bonding among clay platelets confer high impact resistance by impeding the propagation of cracks through the material. This modified clay could be employed to reinforce natural fiber/polypropylene composite also.

References

- [1] X.L. Xie, Z.Z. Yu, Q.X. Zhang, G.W. Zheng, Y.W. Mai E. Berry and K. Current “Synergistic effect of SEBS-g-MA and epoxy on toughening of polyamide 6/glass fiber composites”. *Journal of polymer science B*, Vol. 45, pp 1448-1458, 2007.
- [2] H.W. Gu, Y.B. Guo, S.Y. Wong, V.P.W. Shim, X. Li “Study of amino-functionalized mesoporous silica

nanoparticles (NH₂-MSN) and polyamide-6 nanocomposites co-incorporated with NH₂-MSN and organo-montmorillonite” *Microporous Mesoporous Materials*, DOI: 10.1016/j.micromeso.2012.12.010.

- [3] K. Wang, L. Wang, J.S. Wu, L. Chen, C.B. He. “Preparation of highly exfoliated epoxy/clay nanocomposites by "slurry compounding": process and mechanisms”. *Langmuir*, Vol. 21, pp 3613-3618, 2005
- [4] N. Phonthammachai, C.B. He, X. Li. “Nanocomposites and process for their production” *US patent*, 2010/0196611 A1, 2010.